

Table S2. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) between physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate and nutritional properties of *Pleurotus ostreatus* mushroom.

Variable		Nutritional properties of <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> mushroom					
		Moisture content	Ash content	Crude protein	Crude fiber	Crude lipid	Beta glucan
Physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate	Wet bulk density	0.783*	0.649	-0.275	0.130	-0.585	-0.665
	Particle density	0.224	0.866**	-0.813**	0.103	-0.251	-0.733*
	Porosity	-0.768*	0.000	-0.517	-0.114	0.492	0.176
	pH	-0.152	-0.293	0.463	0.282	0.136	0.346
	Moisture content	0.197	0.240	0.082	0.025	-0.165	-0.275
	Ash content	0.718*	0.207	0.284	-0.228	-0.095	-0.124
	Volatile solids content	-0.718*	-0.207	-0.284	0.228	0.095	0.124
	Nitrogen	0.563	0.259	0.168	0.036	-0.056	-0.166
	Phosphorus	0.458	0.084	0.467	-0.550	0.082	0.005
	Potassium	0.013	-0.494	0.706*	-0.635	0.314	0.701*
	Calcium	0.264	-0.072	0.459	-0.473	0.308	-0.027
	Magnesium	0.303	-0.121	0.568	-0.563	0.254	0.105
	Iron	0.258	-0.176	0.276	-0.252	-0.230	0.335
	Zinc	0.463	0.284	0.034	-0.167	-0.262	0.229
	Carbon	-0.359	0.306	-0.575	0.070	0.085	-0.016
	Lignin	0.020	0.606	-0.901**	0.498	-0.263	-0.615
	Hemicellulose	-0.166	-0.301	0.048	-0.231	-0.016	0.467
	Cellulose	-0.153	0.211	-0.292	-0.213	0.490	0.019

Note:

** Significantly correlated at $p \leq 0.01$

* Significantly correlated at $p \leq 0.05$